

An updated list of bee species (Hymenoptera: Apoidea) found in West Bengal, India along with two new state records

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Abstract

The present study provides an updated list of bee species found in West Bengal, India. The list includes 137 species, belonging to 32 genera under 5 families. The paper also reports new state records of 2 bee species namely *Ceratina* (*Ceratinidia*) *compacta* (Smith) and *Megachile* (*Callomegachile*) *umbripennis* (Smith), along with data on their floral associations. The present study could observe an invasive plant species serving as an alternative food resource for bees when the native species is absent.

Keywords: Bees, Pollinators, Apoidea, Hymenoptera.

Received: 26 July 2022; Revised: 30 December 2022; Online: 31 December 2022

Introduction

Bees are important ecosystem service providers and are considered to be the most effective of all insects in their role as pollinators (Raj *et al.*, 2012; Matias *et al.*, 2017). They are the primary pollinators of several plant species, both crop and non-crop. Pollination services provided by pollinators such as bees, birds and bats account for approximately 35% of the global agricultural produce (Klein *et al.*, 2007). The global bee population is on the decline triggered by anthropogenic effects like deforestation, habitat fragmentation and degradation, land conversion, global warming, climate change and extensive pesticide use in agriculture, which together have led to a scarcity of quality habitat holding ample food resource for bees (Potts *et al.*, 2010). Declining bee population and diversity has led to a sharp dip in pollination services, further contributing to pollen-limited fecundity among plants in natural communities with up to 62% of plants experiencing pollen deficit (Ashman *et al.*, 2004). So, it becomes important at this current scenario to gather ample information on the occurrence and distribution of bee species in regions across the globe so that future conservation efforts could be properly oriented towards reducing the recent biodiversity loss.

The global database reports the presence of 20,507 bee species in the world (Ascher and Pickering, 2022) distributed across 7 families namely Andrenidae, Apidae, Colletidae, Halictidae, Megachilidae, Melittidae and Stenotritidae (Michener, 2007). In India, about 796 bee species have been described so far in 71 genera under 6 families; 50 species in 1 genus from family Andrenidae, 225 species in 25 genera from family Apidae, 31 species in 2 genera from family Colletidae, 216 species in 14 genera from family Halictidae, 270 species in 27 genera from family Megachilidae and 4 species in 2 genera from Melittidae (Pannure and Belavadi, 2019; Ascher and Pickering, 2022).

Among all Indian states, although West Bengal is well known as an agrarian State, having cropping intensity of 184% and cultivating numerous pollinator dependent crop (West Bengal State Portal, 2022). However, a checklist of bees reported from the state is lacking. Even information and literature regarding these pollinators are very less and remain scattered. To fill up this knowledge lacuna, the present study attempts to provide an updated list of bee species found in the Indian state of West Bengal. In consort with the list, it also reports new distribution records of two bee species *Ceratina*

(*Ceratinidia*) *compacta* (Smith, 1879) (Family- Apidae) and *Megachile* (*Callomegachile*) *umbripennis* (Smith, 1853) (Family- Megachilidae) from West Bengal, India.

Materials and Methods

Study Site:

Intensive collections for bee specimens were

made from Batanagar, a township in Maheshtala, Kolkata, South 24 Parganas and Acharya Jagadish Chandra Bose Indian Botanic Garden, Shibpur, Howrah of West Bengal, India during the month of September to December, 2021. These two sites may be characterized as urban green spaces. Coordinates of the study plot were taken using GPS (Model: Garmin GPSmap-76CSx).

Figure 1: Habitat shot of AJC Bose, Indian Botanic Garden, Howrah

Figure 2: Habitat shot of Batanagar, West Bengal

Figure 3: Percentage representation of different families of bees in West Bengal, India

The weather conditions varied from clouds and haze with intermittent rains during the months of September and October to fairly good weather with morning fogs during the months of November and December. Temperature and relative humidity varied between to 23°C to 32°C and 46% to 86%, respectively, during the study days.

The species list was prepared by literature survey and also based on recent bee collections made by the authors.

The specimens were collected using sweep net sampling. The collected bees were

first killed in a killing jar containing cotton wool dabbled in ethyl acetate. The dead specimens were rinsed thoroughly with distilled water and then transferred to vials with absolute alcohol for preservation. In the laboratory, specimens were relaxed, stretched and pinned for identification.

Collected specimens were studied in detail under a stereomicroscope (Leica EZ4HD). Photomicrographs were obtained using a LEICA DFC 500 digital camera attached to LEICA M205 stereomicroscope (1X objective) and processed with LAS

An updated list of bee species found in West Bengal, India

version 3.6 extended focus software. The image plate was further processed by the Adobe Photoshop CC. The bee specimens were identified to species level. The classification followed Michener (2007). Voucher specimens are deposited at the National Zoological Collection (NZC), Zoological Survey of India, Kolkata.

Results

The current report gives an account of the bee species found in the state of West Bengal, India. A total of 137 species under 32 genera belonging to 5 families are recorded. The maximum number of bees were reported from Apidae (47%), followed by Halictidae (28%), Megachilidae (21%), Colletidae (3%), Andrenidae (1%) (Table 1).

Table 1: An updated checklist of Bees (Hymenoptera: Apoidea) from the state of West Bengal

Sl. No.	Species name	Reference
Family – Andrenidae		
Subfamily- Andreninae		
Tribe- Andrenini		
1	<i>Andrena gracillima</i> (Cameron, 1897)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
Family – Apidae		
Subfamily- Apinae		
Tribe- Anthophorini		
2	<i>Amegilla (Amegilla) confusa</i> (Smith, 1854)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
3	<i>Amegilla (Dizonamegilla) dizona</i> (Engel, 2009)	Bingham and Morley, 1897
4	<i>Amegilla (Glossamegilla) himalajensis</i> (Radoszkowski, 1882)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
5	<i>Amegilla (Glossamegilla) violacea</i> (Lepeletier, 1841)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
6	<i>Amegilla (Zonamegilla) niveocincta</i> (Smith, 1854)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
7	<i>Amegilla (Zonamegilla) zonata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Layek <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Saini <i>et al.</i> , 2018
8	<i>Elaphropoda nuda</i> (Radoszkowski, 1882)	Saini <i>et al.</i> , 2021
9	<i>Habropoda krishna</i> (Bingham, 1908)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
10	<i>Habropoda radoszkowskii</i> (Dalla Torre, 1896)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
Tribe- Apini		
11	<i>Apis (Apis) cerana</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
12	<i>Apis (Apis) mellifera</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
13	<i>Apis (Megapis) dorsata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
14	<i>Apis (Megapis) laboriosa</i> (Smith, 1871)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
15	<i>Apis (Micrapis) andreniformis</i> (Smith, 1858)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
16	<i>Apis (Micrapis) florea</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
Tribe- Bombini		
17	<i>Bombus (Megabombus) albopleuralis</i> (Friese, 1916)	Willams, 2022
18	<i>Bombus (Alpigenobombus) breviceps</i> (Smith, 1852)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
19	<i>Bombus (Alpigenobombus) genalis</i> (Friese, 1918)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
20	<i>Bombus (Bombus) tunicatus</i> (Smith, 1852)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
21	<i>Bombus parthenius</i> (Richards, 1934)	Willams, 2022
22	<i>Bombus (Melanobombus) eximius</i> (Smith, 1852)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
23	<i>Bombus (Melanobombus) festivus</i> (Smith, 1861)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
24	<i>Bombus (Orientalibombus) funerarius</i> (Smith, 1852)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
25	<i>Bombus (Orientalibombus) haemorrhoidalis</i> (Smith, 1852)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
26	<i>Bombus (Pyrobombus) abnormis</i> (Tkalcù, 1968)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
27	<i>Bombus (Pyrobombus) flavescens</i> (Smith, 1852)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
28	<i>Bombus (Pyrobombus) luteipes</i> (Richards, 1934)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
29	<i>Bombus (Pyrobombus) pressus</i> (Frison, 1935)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022

30	<i>Bombus (Pyrobombus) rotundiceps</i> (Friese, 1916)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
Tribe- Melectini		
31	<i>Tetralonioidella himalayana</i> (Bingham, 1897)	Chandra <i>et al.</i> , 2021
32	<i>Thyreus himalayensis</i> (Radoszkowski, 1893)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
33	<i>Thyreus histrio</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
34	<i>Thyreus massuri</i> (Radoszkowski, 1893)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
35	<i>Thyreus novaehollandiae</i> (Lepelletier, 1841)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
36	<i>Thyreus praestans</i> (Lieftinck, 1962)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
37	<i>Thyreus smithii</i> (Dalla Torre, 1896)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
38	<i>Thyreus surniculus</i> (Lieftinck, 1959)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
39	<i>Thyreus takaonis</i> (Cockerell, 1911)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
Tribe- Meliponini		
40	<i>Lepidotrigona arcifera</i> (Cockerell, 1929)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
41	<i>Tetragonula (Tetragonula) bengalensis</i> (Cameron, 1897)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
42	<i>Tetragonula (Tetragonula) iridipennis</i> (Smith, 1854)	Chandra <i>et al.</i> , 2021
Tribe- Nomadini		
43	<i>Nomada adusta</i> (Smith, 1875)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
44	<i>Nomada turneri</i> (Meade-Waldo, 1913)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
Subfamily- Xylocopinae		
Tribe- Allodapini		
45	<i>Braunsapis mixta</i> (Smith, 1852)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
46	<i>Braunsapis puangensis</i> (Cockerell, 1929)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
47	<i>Braunsapis picitarsis</i> (Cameron, 1902)	Chandra <i>et al.</i> , 2022
Tribe- Ceratinini		
48	<i>Ceratina bhawani</i> (Bingham, 1908)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
49	<i>Ceratina (Ceratinidia) compacta</i> (Smith, 1879)	New record
50	<i>Ceratina (Ceratinidia) hieroglyphica</i> (Smith, 1854)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
51	<i>Ceratina (Pithitis) binghami</i> (Cockerell, 1908)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
Tribe- Xylocopini		
52	<i>Xylocopa (Biluna) auripennis</i> (Lepelletier, 1841)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
53	<i>Xylocopa (Biluna) nasalis</i> (Westwood, 1842)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
54	<i>Xylocopa (Biluna) tranquebarorum</i> (Swederus, 1787)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
55	<i>Xylocopa (Ctenoxylocopa) fenestrata</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
56	<i>Xylocopa (Hoploxylocopa) acutipennis</i> (Smith, 1854)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
57	<i>Xylocopa (Koptortosoma) aestuans</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
58	<i>Xylocopa (Koptortosoma) flavonigrescens</i> (Smith, 1854)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
59	<i>Xylocopa (Koptortosoma) pubescens</i> (Spinola, 1838)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
60	<i>Xylocopa (Koptortosoma) ruficornis</i> (Fabricius, 1804)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
61	<i>Xylocopa (Maaiana) bentoni</i> (Cockerell, 1919)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
62	<i>Xylocopa (Nyctomelitta) tranquebarica</i> (Fabricius, 1804)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
63	<i>Xylocopa (Platynopoda) latipes</i> (Drury, 1773)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
64	<i>Xylocopa (Platynopoda) magnifica</i> (Cockerell, 1929)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
65	<i>Xylocopa (Platynopoda) tenuiscapa</i> (Westwood, 1840)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
66	<i>Xylocopa (Zonohirsuta) dejeanii</i> (Lepelletier, 1841)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
Family – Colletidae		
Subfamily- Hylaeinae		
67	<i>Hylaeus basimacula</i> (Cameron, 1904)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
68	<i>Hylaeus (Indialaeus) bellicosus</i> (Cameron, 1897)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
69	<i>Hylaeus (Indialaeus) strenuus</i> (Cameron, 1897)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
70	<i>Hylaeus (Prosopis) montanus</i> (Nurse, 1903)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022

An updated list of bee species found in West Bengal, India

Family – Halictidae		
Subfamily- Halictinae		
Tribe- Halictini		
71	<i>Halictus acrocephalus</i> (Blüthgen, 1926)	Layek <i>et al.</i> , 2021
72	<i>Halictus (Seladonia) lucidipennis</i> (Smith, 1853)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
73	<i>Halictus (Seladonia) propinquus</i> (Smith, 1853)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
74	<i>Lasioglossum (Ctenonomia) albescens</i> (Smith, 1853)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
75	<i>Lasioglossum (Ctenonomia) ciris</i> (Cameron, 1897)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
76	<i>Lasioglossum (Ctenonomia) compressum</i> (Blüthgen, 1926)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
77	<i>Lasioglossum (Ctenonomia) pashokense</i> (Blüthgen, 1926)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
78	<i>Lasioglossum (Ctenonomia) sikkimense</i> (Blüthgen, 1926)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
79	<i>Lasioglossum (Ctenonomia) splendidulum</i> (Vachal, 1895)	Chandra <i>et al.</i> , 2021
80	<i>Lasioglossum (Dialictus) sanitarium</i> (Blüthgen, 1926)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
81	<i>Lasioglossum (Evylaeus) funebre</i> (Cameron, 1897)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
82	<i>Lasioglossum (Evylaeus) pseudopalmeri</i> (Blüthgen, 1926)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
83	<i>Lasioglossum (Evylaeus) salutatrix</i> (Cameron, 1897)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
84	<i>Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) cavillosum</i> (Vachal, 1895)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
85	<i>Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) eduardi</i> (Blüthgen, 1931)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
86	<i>Lasioglossum (Leuchalictus) dynastes</i> (Bingham, 1898)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
87	<i>Lasioglossum (Sphecodogastra) perihirtulum</i> (Cockerell, 1937)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
88	<i>Patellapis (Pachyhalictus) interstitialis</i> (Cameron, 1903)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
89	<i>Sphecodes crassicornis</i> (Smith, 1879)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022; Bingham and Morley, 1897
90	<i>Sphecodes chaprensis</i> (Blüthgen, 1927)	Rajkumar and Dey, 2016
91	<i>Thrinchostoma wroughtoni</i> (Cameron, 1897)	Bingham and Morley, 1897
Subfamily- Nomiinae		
Tribe- Nomiini		
92	<i>Lipotriches (Austronomia) albofimbriata</i> (Cameron, 1902)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
93	<i>Lipotriches (Austronomia) scutellata</i> (Smith, 1875)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
94	<i>Lipotriches (Lipotriches) fulvinerva</i> (Cameron, 1907)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
95	<i>Lipotriches (Lipotriches) phenacopsis</i> (Cockerell, 1911)	Majumder <i>et al.</i> , 2021
96	<i>Lipotriches (Rhopalomelissa) pulchriventris</i> (Cameron, 1897)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
97	<i>Nomia (Acunomia) iridescens</i> (Smith, 1857)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
98	<i>Nomia (Acunomia) strigata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022; Bhattacharyya <i>et al.</i> , 2019
99	<i>Nomia (Crocisaspidia) buddha</i> (Westwood, 1875)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
100	<i>Nomia (Gnathonomia) thoracica</i> (Smith, 1875)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
101	<i>Nomia (Hoplonomia) elliotii</i> (Smith, 1875)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
102	<i>Nomia (Hoplonomia) westwoodi</i> (Gribodo, 1894)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
103	<i>Nomia (Maculonomia) anthophoroides</i> (Meade-Waldo, 1916)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
104	<i>Nomia (Nomia) curvipes</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
105	<i>Pseudapis (Pseudapis) oxybeloides</i> (Smith, 1875)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
106	<i>Steganomus bipunctatus</i> (Fabricius, 1804)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022

107	<i>Steganomus lieftincki</i> (Pauly, 2009)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
108	<i>Steganomus nodicornis</i> (Smith, 1875)	Dover, 1921
Family – Megachilidae		
Subfamily- Megachilinae		
Tribe- Anthidiini		
109	<i>Anthidiellum (Pycnanthidium) rasorium</i> (Smith, 1875)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
110	<i>Bathanthidium (Manthidium) binghami</i> (Friese, 1901)	Sardar <i>et al.</i> , 2022
111	<i>Euaspis carbonaria</i> (Smith, 1854)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
112	<i>Euaspis edentata</i> (Baker, 1995)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
113	<i>Stelis bengala</i> (Warncke, 1992)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
114	<i>Trachusa longicornis</i> (Friese, 1902)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
Tribe- Megachilini		
115	<i>Coelioxys (Allocoelioxys) capitatus</i> (Smith, 1854)	Bingham and Morley, 1897
116	<i>Coelioxys (Allocoelioxys) cuneatus</i> (Smith, 1875)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
117	<i>Coelioxys (Callosarissa) confusus</i> (Smith, 1875)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
118	<i>Coelioxys (Liothyrapis) apicatus</i> (Smith, 1854)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
119	<i>Coelioxys (Liothyrapis) decipiens</i> (Spinola, 1838)	Chandra <i>et al.</i> , 2021
120	<i>Coelioxys (Torridapis) fenestratus</i> (Smith, 1873)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
121	<i>Coelioxys (Allocoelioxys) fuscipennis</i> (Smith, 1854)	Dover, 1921
122	<i>Heriades (Michenerella) parvula</i> (Bingham, 1897)	Chandra <i>et al.</i> , 2021
123	<i>Megachile (Aethomegachile) laticeps</i> (Smith, 1853)	Sardar <i>et al.</i> , 2021
124	<i>Megachile (Amegachile) bicolor</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	Chandra <i>et al.</i> , 2021
125	<i>Megachile (Callomegachile) cephalotes</i> (Smith, 1853)	Chandra <i>et al.</i> , 2021
126	<i>Megachile (Aethomegachile) conjuncta</i> (Smith, 1853)	Kumari <i>et al.</i> , 2018
127	<i>Megachile (Callomegachile) disjuncta</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022; Sardar <i>et al.</i> , 2021
128	<i>Megachile (Callomegachile) monticola</i> (Smith, 1853)	Chandra <i>et al.</i> , 2022
129	<i>Megachile (Callomegachile) relata</i> (Smith, 1879)	Chandra <i>et al.</i> , 2021
130	<i>Megachile (Callomegachile) umbripennis</i> (Smith, 1853)	New record
131	<i>Megachile (Eutricharaea) coelioxysides</i> (Bingham, 1898)	Sardar <i>et al.</i> , 2021
132	<i>Megachile (Eutricharaea) gathela</i> (Cameron, 1908)	Chandra <i>et al.</i> , 2021
133	<i>Megachile (Eutricharaea) hera</i> (Bingham, 1897)	Gupta, 2013
134	<i>Megachile (Eutricharaea) vera</i> (Nurse, 1901)	Sardar <i>et al.</i> , 2021
135	<i>Megachile femoratella</i> (Cockerell, 1918)	Ascher and Pickering, 2022
136	<i>Megachile (Pseudomegachile) lanata</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Sardar <i>et al.</i> , 2021
137	<i>Megachile (Xanthosarus) anthracina</i> (Smith, 1853)	Bingham and Morley, 1897

1. *Ceratina (Ceratinidia) compacta* (Smith, 1879)

Synonyms- *Ceratina philippinensis* Ashmead, 1904

Material examined: 01 ♂, India, West Bengal, Batanagar, 22°30'47"N 88°13'03"E, 27.ix.2021, sweep net, coll. D. Dey; 01 ♀, India, West Bengal, Batanagar, 22°30'47"N 88°13'03"E, 27.ix.2021, sweep net, coll. D. Dey; 01 ♀, India, West Bengal, Batanagar, 22°30'40"N 88°13'18"E, 06.xi.2021, sweep net, coll. D. Dey; 01 ♀, India, West Bengal, Batanagar, 22°30'40"N 88°13'18"E, 06.xi.2021, sweep net, coll. D. Dey; 01 ♀, India, West Bengal, Batanagar, 22°30'40"N 88°13'18"E, 01.xii.2021, sweep net, coll. D.

New state reports

Based on the present study, two bee species viz., *Ceratina (Ceratinidia) compacta* (Family- Apidae) and *Megachile (Callomegachile) umbripennis* (Family- Megachilidae) are reported for the first time from West Bengal, India.

Taxonomy Family APIDAE

Subfamily XYLOCOPINAE

Tribe Ceratinini

Genus *Ceratina* Latreille, 1802

- I. Subgenus *Ceratinidia* (Cockerell and Porter, 1899)

Dey; 01 ♀, India, West Bengal, Batanagar, 22°30'41"N 88°13'19"E, 26.xii.2021, sweep net, coll. D. Dey.

Distribution: India: Uttarakhand (Khan and Yogi, 2020) and West Bengal (new record).

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, China, Hong Kong, Thailand, Malaysia, Indonesia, Philippines (Ascher and Pickering, 2022).

Floral associations in India: *Cajanus cajan* (Fabaceae), *Helianthus annuus* (Asteraceae), *Brassica juncea* (Brassicaceae), *Luffa* sp. (Cucurbitaceae) (Yogi and Khan, 2020); *Anisomeles indica* (Lamiaceae), *Sphagneticola trilobata*, *Tridax procumbens*, *Chromolaena odorata* (Asteraceae) (Present study).

Family MEGACHILIDAE
Subfamily MEGACHILINAE
Tribe Megachilini
Genus *Megachile*

II. Subgenus *Callomegachile* (Michener, 2007)

2. *Megachile (Callomegachile) umbripennis* (Smith, 1853)

Synonyms- *Megachile schauinslandi* (Alfken, 1898); *Megachile domesticum* (Perkins, 1899), nomen nudum; *Megachile umbripennis* var *atriventris* homonym (Friese, 1903); *Megachile aureobasis* (Cockerell, 1919); *Megachile (Eumegachile) umbripennis* (Smith, 1853); *Chalicodoma (Callomegachile) umbripenne* (Smith, 1853)

Material examined: 01 ♀, India, West Bengal, Batanagar, 22°30'40"N 88°13'18"E, 06.xi.2021, sweep net, coll. D. Dey; 01 ♀, India, West Bengal, Batanagar, 22°30'40"N 88°13'18"E, 26.xi.2021, sweep net, coll. D. Dey; 01 ♀, India, West Bengal, Batanagar, 22°30'40"N 88°13'18"E, 26.xi.2021, sweep net, coll. D. Dey; 01 ♂, India, West Bengal, Howrah: Shibpur: Acharya Jagadish Chandra Bose Indian Botanic Garden, 22°33'25"N 88°17'55"E, 23.xi.2021, sweep net, coll. D. Dey; 01 ♀, India, West Bengal, Howrah: Shibpur: Acharya Jagadish Chandra Bose Indian Botanic Garden, 22°33'25"N 88°17'55"E, 03.xii.2021, sweep net, coll. D. Dey; 01 ♂, India, West Bengal, Batanagar,

22°30'41"N 88°13'19"E, 14.xii.2021, sweep net, coll. D. Dey; 01 ♂, India, West Bengal, Batanagar, 22°30'41"N 88°13'19"E, 14.xii.2021, sweep net, coll. D. Dey; 01 ♂, India, West Bengal, Batanagar, 22°30'41"N 88°13'19"E, 26.xii.2021, sweep net, coll. D. Dey.

Distribution: India: Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Haryana, Chandigarh, Gujarat, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Arunachal Pradesh, Sikkim (Saini *et al.*, 2018) and West Bengal (New record).

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka, Nepal, Bangladesh, Myanmar, China, Hong Kong, Thailand, Laos, Vietnam, Malaysia, Singapore, Cook Islands, France, USA (Ascher and Pickering, 2022).

Floral associations in India: *Bauhinia tomentosa*, *Lupinus perennis*, *Consolida ajacis*, *Vigna radiata*, *Vigna mungo*, *Justicia gengarussa*, *Pongamia pinnata*, *Cosmos sulphurous*, *Tanacetum cinerariifolium*, *Dalbergia latifolia*, *Salvia viridis*, *Bauhinia acuminata*, *Caesalpinia pulcherrima*, *Cajanus cajan* (Fabaceae), *Cuphea hyssopifolia* (Kunjwal *et al.*, 2021); *Anisomeles indica* (Lamiaceae), *Asystasia indica* (Acanthaceae), *Chromolaena odorata* (Asteraceae) (Present study).

Discussion

Among the 137 bee species of West Bengal, 12 species viz., *Hylaeus (Indialaeus) bellicosus* Cameron, 1897, *Hylaeus basimacula* Cameron, 1904, *Lasioglossum (Ctenonomia) pashokense* Blüthgen, 1926, *Patellapis (Pachyhalictus) interstitialis* Cameron, 1903, *Thrinchostoma wroughtoni* Cameron, 1897, *Lipotriches (Austronomia) albofimbriata* Cameron, 1902, *Lipotriches (Austronomia) scutellata* Smith, 1875, *Nomia (Maculonomia) anthophoroides* Meade-Waldo, 1916, *Stelis bengala* Warncke, 1992, *Coelioxys (Torridapis) fenestratus* Smith, 1873, *Thyreus novaehollandiae* Lepelletier, 1841, *Thyreus praestans* Lieftinck, 1962, are reported exclusively from West Bengal only.

The present study also adds new records of two bee species to West Bengal, India. Till date *Ceratina compacta* is known

Figure 4: Field photograph of *C. compacta*

Figure 6: Field photograph of *M. umbripennis*

Figure 5: Microscopic profile image of *C. compacta* (dorsal view)

Figure 7: Microscopic profile image of *M. umbripennis* (dorsal view)

only from the state of Uttarakhand, India. Khan and Yogi (2020) reported for the first time the presence of *C. compacta* in India which portrayed the range expansion of the bee species in Asian countries.

The current study, also reports the leafcutter bee *Megachile umbripennis* from West Bengal for the first time. *M. umbripennis* is widely distributed in South East Asian countries as well as the different Indian states (Ascher and Pickering, 2022).

The present study could observe *M. umbripennis* foraging on the native plants like *Anisomeles indica* and *Asystasia indica* during the month of November. While in December *M. umbripennis* was observed visiting flowers of the invasive alien plant species *Chromolaena odorata*. The native plant *Anisomeles indica* and the invasive *Chromolaena odorata* co-occurred at the study site of Batanagar but *C. odorata* only started flowering in late November while *Anisomeles indica* had already set seed and flowering was very sparse with higher sporadicity. An interesting observation is worth mentioning here. Visits by *M. umbripennis* to both the flowering plant species and their flowering period suggest that the invasive plant serves as an important alternative floral resource when the native plant is not flowering.

To maintain the flow of effective pollination services, the management and conservation of bee species are essential and it can primarily be achieved by obtaining ample knowledge on their distribution. Research lacuna regarding habitat requirements, ecological interaction of these pollinators need to be addressed. This study provides first line of information on bees of West Bengal, which will help in their future research and conservation.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the Director, Zoological Survey of India, Kolkata; Prof. Parthiba Basu, Ecology Research Unit, Department of Zoology, University of Calcutta and Miscellaneous Insect Order Section, ZSI-Kolkata for continuous encouragement and providing necessary help and support to carry out the work. The first author is thankful to the Zoological Society, Kolkata, National Internship Award (2021). Along with that, the corresponding author would like to thank the Council of Scientific & Industrial Research (CSIR), India for research funding.

References

Ascher, J.S. and Pickering, J. 2022. Discover Life bee species guide and world

An updated list of bee species found in West Bengal, India

- checklist (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Anthophila). Accessed online on 20.06.2022 at http://www.discoverlife.org/mp/20q?guide=Apoidea_species
- Ashman, T.L., Knight, T.M., Steets, J.S., Amarasekare, P., Burd, M., Campbell, D.R., Dudash, M.R., Johnston, M.O., Mazer, S.J., Mitchell, R.J., Morgan, M.T. and Wilson, W.G. 2004. Pollen limitation of plant reproduction: ecological and evolutionary causes and consequences. *Ecology* 85(9): 2408-2421.
- Bhattacharyya, M., Bhattacharya, M.Kr., Chakraborty, K.S. and Acharya, S.Kr. 2019. Bee sampling efficiencies of three different methods in a forested ecosystem in Southern West Bengal, India: A comparative study. *Ecology, Environment and Conservation* 25(1): 269-276.
- Bingham, C.T. and Morley, C. 1897. The Fauna of British India, Including Ceylon and Burma. Hymenoptera-Vol. 1. Wasps and Bees. London: Taylor & Francis. 579pp.
- Chandra, K., Banerjee, D., Raghunathan, C., Gupta, D., Rai, P. and Sharma, G. 2022. Faunal Diversity of Biogeographic Zones of India: Gangetic Plains. Kolkata: Director, Zool. Surv. India. 1-369pp. ISBN 978-81-8171-582-1
- Chandra, K., Saini, J. and Gupta, D. 2021. Insecta: Hymenoptera: Apoidea (Bees). *In: Fauna of Himachal Pradesh, State Fauna Series*. Kolkata: Director, Zoological Survey of India, 26 (Part-1): 505-524.
- Dover, C. 1921. The Wasps and Bees of Barkuda Island https://digitalcommons.usu.edu/bee_lab_d/263
- Gupta, R.K. 2013. The leaf-cutting bee *M. bicolor* (Fabricius) (Insecta: Hymenoptera, Megachilidae), an important cross pollinator for many cultivated and wild crops in northern India. *Journal of Environment and Bio-Sciences* 27: 271–276.
- Khan, M. and Yogi, M. 2020. New record of a small carpenter bee, *Ceratina compacta* Smith (Hymenoptera: Apidae) from India. *Journal of Apicultural Research* 60: 1-3.
- Klein, A.M., Vaissière, B.E., Cane, J.H., Steffan-Dewenter, I., Cunningham, S.A., Kremen, C. and Tscharntke, T. 2007. Importance of pollinators in changing landscapes for world crops. *Proceedings of the royal society B: biological sciences* 274(1608): 303-313.
- Kumari, P., Kumar, N.R., Sidhu, A.K. and Chandra, K. 2018. Taxonomical and behavioural studies on *Megachile conjuncta* (Fabricius) (Hymenoptera: Megachilidae: Cressoniella). *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies* 6: 2198-2201.
- Kunjwal, N., Khan, M.S., Kumar, G. and Srivastava, P. 2021. Notes on the nesting ecology of the *Megachile* bees from North India. *Journal of Apicultural Research* 60(5): 807-816.
- Layek, U., Kundu, A., Bisui, S. and Karmakar, P. 2021. Impact of managed stingless bee and western honey bee colonies on native pollinators and yield of watermelon: A comparative study. *Annals of Agricultural Sciences* 66: 38–45.
- Majumder, B. Rameshkumar, A. and Kazmi, S.I. 2021. Bees of grasses, *Lipotriches* Gerstaecker, Sweat bees, *Steganomus* Ritsema and *Crociaspidia* Ashmead (Halictidae: Nomiinae), with new distribution report from Indian states. *Journal of Entomological Research* 44(4): 589-593.
- Matias, D.M.S., Leventon, J., Rau, A.L., Borgemeister, C., and von Wehrden, H. 2017. A review of ecosystem service benefits from wild bees across social contexts. *Ambio* 46(4): 456-467.
- Michener, C.D. 2007. The bees of the world, 2nd revised edition. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Pannure, A. and Belavadi, V.V. 2019. Status and Diversity of Pollinators in India- a case study for Conserving Non-Apis Bees. *ENVIS Newsletter, ZSI, Kolkata*, 25: 1-4.
- Potts, S.G., Biesmeijer, J.C., Kremen, C., Neumann, P., Schweiger, O. and Kunin, W.E. 2010. Global pollinator declines: trends, impacts and drivers. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution* 25(6): 345-353.
- Raj, H., Mattu, V.K. and Thakur, M.L. 2012. Pollinator diversity and relative abundance of insect visitors on apple crop in Shimla hills of western Himalaya, India. *International Journal of Science and Nature* 3(3): 507-513.

- Rajkumar, M.B. and Dey, D. 2016. Identification and description of Indian parasitic bee genus *Sphcodes* Latreille 1804, (Halictidae: Hymenoptera). Journal of Applied and Natural Science 8(4): 1839-1849.
- Saini, J., Chandra, K., Kumar, H. and Hooda, S. 2021. Two new species of genus *Elaphropoda* lieftinck, 1966 (Hymenoptera: Apoidea, Apidae: Apinae: Anthophorini) from Arunachal Pradesh, India. Journal of Entomological Research 45(4): 765-768.
- Saini, J., Chandra, K., Kumar, H., Ghosh, D.J., Kazmi, S.I., Payra, A. and Deepak, C.K. 2018. Diversity of Bees (Hymenoptera: Apoidea) in and around Namdapha National Park, with an Updated Checklist from Arunachal Pradesh, India. Recordings of Zoological Survey of India 118(4): 413-425.
- Sardar, S., Kasperek, M., Rameshkumar, A. and Kazmi, S. 2022. Four species of anthidiine bees (Apoidea: Megachilidae) new to India. The Canadian Entomologist 154(1), E7.
- Sardar, S., Warrit, N., Rameshkumar, A. and Kazmi, S.I. 2021. New distributional records of *Megachile* Latreille, 1802 (Apoidea: Megachilidae) from Indian States. Recordings of Zoological Survey of India 121(1): 23–29.
- Smith, F. 1853. Catalogue of hymenopterous insects in the collection of the British museum. Part 1. Andrenidae and Apidae. London: Taylor and Francis. 1-440 pp.
- Smith, F. 1858. Catalogue of the hymenopterous insects collected at Sarawak, Borneo; Mount Ophir, Malacca; and at Singapore, by A R Wallace. Proceedings of the Linnaean Society of London 2: 42-130.
- WBSP. 2022. West Bengal State Portal (WBSP), 2022. Accessed online at <https://wb.gov.in/departments-details.aspx?id=D170907140022669&page=Agriculture>
- Williams, P.H. 2022. The Bumblebees of the Himalaya- An Identification. AbcTaxa 21: 175-176.
- Williams, P.H., Ito, M., Matsumura, T. and Kudo, I. 2010. The bumblebees of the Nepal Himalaya (Hymenoptera: Apidae). Insecta matsumurana. New series: Journal of the Faculty of Agriculture Hokkaido University, series entomology 66: 115-151.